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ABSTRACT

Surfaces of cubic perovskite oxides attract significant attention for their physical tunability and high potential for technical applications. Bulk-terminated surfaces are desirable for theoretical modeling and experimental reproducibility, yet there is a lack of methods for preparing such well-defined surfaces. We discuss a method for strain-assisted cleaving of perovskite single crystals, using a setup easily transferable between different experimental systems. The details of the cleaving device and the procedure were optimized in a systematic study on the model cubic perovskite oxide SrTiO₃. The large-area morphology and typical distribution of surface terminations on cleaved SrTiO₃(001) are presented, with specific guidelines on how to distinguish well-cleaved surfaces from conchoidally fractured ones. The cleaving is applicable to other cubic perovskites, as demonstrated on KTaO₃(001) and BaTiO₃(001). This approach opens up a pathway for obtaining high-quality surfaces of this promising class of materials.

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INTRODUCTION

Cleaving is a preferred preparation method for many surfaces because cleaving *in situ*, *i.e.*, in ultra-high vacuum (UHV), creates perfectly clean surfaces that do not require further treatment.^{1–8}

A wide range of solids with preferable cleavage planes readily cleave:⁹ two-dimensional materials such as graphite and graphene cleave/peel¹⁰ by breaking the inter-layer van der Waals forces. Layered materials like muscovite mica^{11,12} or any member of the Ruddlesden–Popper perovskite series¹³ cleave along the layer-separating planes. Ionic crystals like NaCl¹⁴ cleave via bond cleavage along the main crystallographic planes. These materials can be cleaved using a sharp blade or can even be exfoliated. On the other hand, materials that do not possess a natural cleavage plane tend to break by conchoidal fracture, *i.e.*, in a direction that does not follow any crystallographic plane, and the resulting surfaces lack well-defined structure. Cubic perovskite oxides, such as strontium titanate SrTiO₃, are a typical example. Since the cleaving of these materials is not straightforward, there is a systematic absence of studies of their well-defined bulk-truncated surfaces in the literature, despite the vast interest in their use in oxide electronics,^{15–18} catalysis,¹⁹ or solid oxide fuel cells.^{20,21} Here, we present a procedure that

efficiently cleaves cubic perovskite oxides and that is readily transferable between different experimental measurement systems. The principle of operation is discussed and demonstrated on SrTiO₃, and successful application to KTaO₃ and BaTiO₃ promises universality.

CLEAVING THICK SrTiO₃ CRYSTALS

Cubic perovskite oxides with the ABO₃ stoichiometry possess inversion symmetry and no natural cleavage planes. Moreover, they are commonly characterized by mixed ionic and covalent bonding within each unit cell: while the A–O interaction is electrostatic, bonds in BO₆ octahedra have a highly covalent character. The model cubic perovskite oxide SrTiO₃ conchoidally fractures when supplied with a strong-enough external force, yielding surfaces that are ill-defined at the atomic level. Recently, we managed to cleave SrTiO₃ single crystals and create atomically flat (001) surfaces^{22,23} by engineering strain in the cleavage region. An optimized setup for cleaving samples in ultra-high vacuum (UHV) is described in Fig. 1. The SrTiO₃ single crystal is pre-strained prior to insertion into the vacuum chamber [see the photos in Fig. 1(a)]. The cleaving device consists of two identical clamps, one of which compresses the sample at the bottom (photo “I”) and the other one at the top

FIG. 1. (a) Concept of the cleaving device. (I) SrTiO₃ crystal clamped at its bottom part; the device is mounted on a flag-type sample holder. (II) The upper part of the crystal is also strained by a mirror-symmetric clamp. (III) Side view on the cleaving device. (IV) Detailed view of the region indicated in “III” with the SrTiO₃ single crystal outlined in yellow. (V) Sketch of the same region. (b) Model showing the impact of the applied strain on the perovskite lattice (see text for details). (c) Simulations of the static strain distribution after pre-straining a SrTiO₃ single crystal with sharp $\langle 001 \rangle$ edges (left) and beveled edges (right). The color scale represents the magnitude of strain. Regions with strain below a certain threshold are rendered transparent to highlight the points of interest. These transparent low-strain regions are strained rather homogeneously.

(photo “II”). Each clamp consists of a larger jaw that is fixed to its respective flag-type sample holder plate and a smaller jaw that compresses the single crystal by tightening the screws connecting the small and the large jaws. The larger jaws are polished under an $\approx 5^\circ$ angle at the face that is oriented toward a single crystal in order to minimize the contact area with the jaw and increase the contact pressure [see “IV” and “V” in Fig. 1(a)]. The single crystal needs to be subjected to sufficient pressure during the pre-straining procedure: a good indicator is the tilting of the sample by $\approx 2^\circ - 5^\circ$ from the surface normal of the bottom sample plate [“V” in Fig. 1(a)] to accommodate for the geometry of the large jaws. The jaws can be fabricated from any material. Austenitic stainless steel provided better results than molybdenum or various aluminum alloys, presumably due to its suitable mechanical properties.

A proposed atomic-scale model of the involved mechanisms is outlined in Fig. 1(b). The strain applied by the clamps compresses the lattice and facilitates its expansion in the perpendicular direction (transverse expansion, Poisson’s ratio). In principle, this can weaken the corresponding bonds along the c axis and support cleavage in the region where the sample is compressed. This mechanism may be, in principle, valid in any material, while perovskites possess properties that further promote the creation of a cleavage plane: At sufficiently high strain, expansion of the lattice constant along the c axis can induce ferroelectric polarization,^{24–27} where the transition metal atom in the center of the cubic cell [Ti in Fig. 1(b)] shifts in direction parallel to the lattice expansion. This leads to a further elongation of one of the covalent bonds in the Ti octahedron and breaking the cubic crystal symmetry. We note that the strain provided solely by the clamps is not sufficient to drive SrTiO₃ to the ferroelectric phase at room temperature; the force applicable by the

used M2 screws is an order of magnitude smaller.^{22,27–29} The ferroelectric polarization can only be driven by the tensile strain present at the tip of the crack that propagates through the crystal. The strain applied by the clamps only plays a supportive role and confines the crack propagation in a well-defined gap between the top and the bottom clamps [“IV” in Fig. 1(a)]. Nevertheless, we found that a proper pre-straining procedure is a necessity for successful cleavage, and the practical aspects of this pre-straining procedure are laid out thoroughly in the Appendix, together with the technical drawings of the cleaving device.

The applied strains are large enough to induce plastic deformation of the steel jaws. The plastic deformation is typically visible as imprints in the steel jaws, and they must be re-polished after each use. Figure 1(c) provides an impression of the strain distribution in the SrTiO₃ crystal. The highest strain appears at the edges of the SrTiO₃ crystal [see the left panel in Fig. 1(c)]. To avoid premature (and ill-defined) cracking at these high-strain points, we use samples with beveled edges parallel to $\langle 001 \rangle$, which result in a more homogeneous strain distribution [see the right panel in Fig. 1(c)]. Using this procedure, we routinely cleave 2 mm thick samples (all surfaces shown in this paper) to create large surface areas, desirable for area-averaging techniques such as x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy or electron diffraction. Thin crystals (below 1 mm) are generally easier to cleave, even if the sharp edges are kept.

CLEAVING PRODUCES TWO RESEARCH-READY SURFACES

Each cleavage creates two mirror-symmetric surfaces, and the double-decker construction with two flag-type sample holders

FIG. 2. Cleaving SrTiO₃(001) produces two mirror-symmetric surfaces. (a)–(c) Secondary electron microscopy (SEM) images obtained on both sides of the same cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface. The morphology is mirrored, and the distribution of surface terminations is the opposite on the two surfaces. The highest-magnification SEM image in (c) is colored for better visibility. (d) Atomically resolved nAFM images of both surface terminations. Panels (a)–(c) were measured on a sample exposed to ambient conditions, while the images in panel (d) were obtained in the same UHV system where the sample was cleaved.

[Fig. 1(a)] enables the utilization of both sides of the cleaved crystals. Figure 2 shows scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of both surfaces side by side. The morphology of the two surfaces is mirrored, and they exhibit an opposite SEM contrast. Cleaving SrTiO₃ along the (001) plane always results in one TiO₂- and one SrO-terminated side, as these are the only possible surface terminations. This leads to symmetry breaking along the [001] direction. Hence, the SEM contrast differences stem from the opposite distribution of surface terminations on the two sides of the same cleaved surface. Namely, if a surface region on one side is TiO₂-terminated, the same region on the other side of a cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface must be terminated with a SrO layer. Although chemically differing in just one atomic layer, the two terminations are recognizable with SEM due to their different work functions and electronic structures: TiO₂ is metallic and SrO semiconducting upon cleavage in UHV.²² For obtaining the SEM images, the samples had to be transported through the air, however, which is likely to modify the surfaces; nevertheless, they show a clearly different brightness in SEM, even after exposing them to ambient conditions for one month.

The SEM images in Figs. 2(a)–2(c) also demonstrate that our SrTiO₃ cleaving procedure creates heterogeneous (001) surfaces. They consist of macroscopically large, alternating domains of metallic and semiconducting material, providing a versatile substrate for applications in electronics or catalysis. In fact, the two terminations likely preferentially adsorb different atmospheric gases, as they can still be recognized even after the cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface was exposed to ambient for a prolonged period of time (up to more than a month) prior to the measurements in Figs. 2(a)–2(c).

The well-cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface areas *a priori* have complementary atomic structures: SrO and TiO₂ terminations are always covered by 0.14 ± 0.02 monolayers of Sr vacancies and adatoms, respectively.²² We have argued that they compensate for the surface polarity during cleaving.²² Figure 2(d) shows atomically resolved

non-contact atomic force microscopy (ncAFM)^{30–33} images of the two terminations, obtained with an O-terminated tip,³⁴ which detects Sr atoms as attractive (dark), O atoms as repulsive (bright), and missing Sr atoms as a lack of attractive interaction (bright “x”-like features). We find that this atomic-scale surface structure is insensitive to details of the preparation. Up until now, we have cleaved more than 40 SrTiO₃ single crystals with 0.5 wt. % of Nb doping, obtained from various vendors (Methods section). The quality of single crystals can affect the quality of cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surfaces only in the relative coverage of well-cleaved areas with respect to conchoidally fractured surface areas. However, the atomic structure of the well-cleaved surface areas was always the same.

RECOGNIZING WELL-CLEAVED SURFACE AREAS ON SrTiO₃(001)

The crack front of a cleavage cannot be controlled during its propagation. It is common that a cleaved surface contains both areas with conchoidal fracture and well-cleaved surfaces; this holds especially true for thick samples where the pre-straining is less efficient. No two cleavages are ever the same, although almost all (>90% of cleaved surfaces) contain at least some well-cleaved regions. The cleaved and fractured portions of a SrTiO₃(001) surface can be readily distinguished with an optical microscope, as shown in Fig. 3. The identification is even easier under a stereo microscope when the angle of illumination can be varied: the samples in Fig. 3 are illuminated under a specific angle where the light is reflected from the flat (001) terraces, highlighting the well-cleaved regions. The best SrTiO₃(001) cleavages are either macroscopically flat (as the one in Ref. 22) or contain many separated, well-cleaved regions of step bunching, as shown in Fig. 3(a). A train of terraces separated by optically visible straight or partially straight steps parallel to each other is a fingerprint of a well-cleaved region [almost all bright regions in

FIG. 3. Distinction between well-cleaved and fractured $\text{SrTiO}_3(001)$ surfaces on optical photographs. Cleaved $\text{SrTiO}_3(001)$ surfaces categorized according to the quality of the cleave: (a) well-cleaved surface regions span the majority of the surface (the first panel shows the whole surface, and the remaining two focus on the details), (b) partially cleaved and partially fractured surfaces (well-cleaved areas are outlined in red), and (c) completely fractured surfaces.

Fig. 3(a) and outlined regions in Fig. 3(b)]. They commonly span hundreds of micrometers or several millimeters [Fig. 2(a)]. Most of these areas have steps running parallel to the force used for pre-straining the crystal (roughly the $[110]$ direction in Fig. 3), but even if not, the steps are always mutually parallel on a well-cleaved surface patch. In contrast, fractured surface regions commonly appear smooth and featureless at a macroscopic scale. The ill-defined surface patches (other than areas highlighted in red in Fig. 3) appear in many flavors, with inconsistent atomic structure and electronic properties. In rare cases, the entire surface fractures and produces a shiny, conchoidal surface, as demonstrated with several examples in

Fig. 3(c). Such surfaces are most commonly a result of insufficient or asymmetric pre-straining that did not enable a controlled crack propagation during cleaving. Successive criteria for distinguishing good from badly cleaved surface areas can be inferred from the systematic overview in Fig. 3: (I) well-cleaved areas reflect light best when illuminated and viewed from the top; when the illumination is not fixed to a $[001]$ axis, all well-cleaved (001) surface regions reflect light simultaneously at certain angles. (II) Well-cleaved areas are not smooth but have optically visible steps separating atomically flat terraces. (III) The steps on well-cleaved areas are parallel to each other and commonly form a terrace train. (IV) If the fractured surface

FIG. 4. Ambient-atmosphere tapping-mode AFM images of cleaved (001) surfaces of three perovskite oxides: (a) and (b) SrTiO₃ (two orientations), (c) KTaO₃, and (d) BaTiO₃. The geometry and the width w of the cleaved single crystals are sketched in the top row; the direction of strain is marked by blue arrows. Line profiles along the red arrows marked in the AFM images are plotted in the bottom row. Note that these large-area images are affected by distortions due to creep of the piezoelectric scanner in the x - y plane; the z -creep has been corrected.

areas are not smooth but have large optically visible steps instead, conchoidal fracture can be recognized by the reflection of light under many different angles due to the random inclination with respect to the [001] surface normal.

The double-decker construction of a cleaving device [Fig. 1] allows removal of one half of the double-decker from a UHV chamber and its characterization with various techniques to provide better guidance for studying the mirror-symmetric counterpart that remains in the UHV chamber. This is a highly desirable option, since the quality of a cleavage and the distribution of well-cleaved areas cannot be predicted *a priori* [Fig. 3]. It ensures that the UHV measurements are performed on well-defined SrTiO₃(001) surfaces instead of the randomly inclined regions of conchoidal fracture, ill-defined at the atomic level, which are unavoidable on any cleaved SrTiO₃(001).

COMPARISON TO OTHER SrTiO₃(001) PREPARATION METHODS

Previous methods for cleaving SrTiO₃(001)^{35–39} were based on hitting a thin (<250 μm thick) SrTiO₃ single crystal in UHV strongly enough that it breaks, preferably at temperatures below the cubic-tetragonal phase transition at 105 K.^{40,41} The double-decker cleaving device (Fig. 1) provides significant improvements to this method. First, cleaving is readily performed at room temperature. Next, thick crystals can be cleaved to yield large (>1 mm²) well-cleaved surface areas suitable for area-averaging methods. Finally, the double-decker construction enables removing the mirror-symmetric counterpart from the UHV, providing the possibility to assess the quality

of the cleave, and directing the measurements on the side that remains in UHV toward properly cleaved surface areas, or performing complementary measurements by different experimental techniques.

Another advantage of our procedure is that a bulk-truncation of SrTiO₃ along the [001] direction is guaranteed in the well-cleaved regions. It overcomes the pitfalls of wet-chemical etching of the cut-and-polished SrTiO₃(001) substrates^{42–44} that can lead to unintentional contamination.⁴⁵ Our approach avoids any cleaning procedures on the SrTiO₃(001), such as sputtering or high-temperature annealing with a CO₂ laser for example.^{46–48} It is known that preserving the SrTiO₃ surface stoichiometry is very difficult following the *in situ* surface cleaning, which commonly leads to surface reconstructions.^{49–54} In fact, we recently showed that the (1 × 1) termination is lost on SrTiO₃(001) substrates treated in UHV, even without sputtering, once the contaminants are thermally removed in UHV, and that the (1 × 1) diffraction pattern in low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) is not indicative of the unreconstructed surface because it can also originate from subsurface layers.²³ The stoichiometry of our well-cleaved surface areas is guaranteed as the cleaving exposes the bulk material. This is a significant challenge in the growth of SrTiO₃ thin films by pulsed laser deposition, where a stoichiometric surface is not guaranteed after material transfer from a stoichiometric SrTiO₃ substrate.^{55,56} Chemical etching removes one of the two terminations,^{49,57–59} while cleaving produces clean, well-defined SrTiO₃(001) surfaces with both TiO₂- and SrO- terminated regions (Fig. 2), a heterogeneous substrate suitable for physical and catalytic characterization.⁶⁰

CLEAVING OTHER CUBIC PEROVSKITE OXIDES

The principles behind cleaving SrTiO₃ with the cleaving device in Fig. 1 seem intrinsic to all (pseudo)cubic perovskite oxides, due to the common flexibility of the B cations in their lattices in response to strain.^{61–64} The AFM images (taken under ambient conditions) in Fig. 4 show cleaved (001) surfaces of SrTiO₃, BaTiO₃, and KTaO₃ achieved through the use of the cleaving device in Fig. 1.

Figure 4(a) shows a result of cleaving a SrTiO₃(001) single crystal in the geometry used throughout this paper, where the compressive strain was applied parallel to the [110] direction. The image was taken on one of the optically visible flat terraces, such as those in Figs. 2 and 3. SrTiO₃ single crystals were also cleaved in a different geometry, where the strain was applied parallel to the [100] direction to a single crystal cut in a way to expose {001} surfaces after cleavage [Fig. 4(b)]. Pre-straining SrTiO₃ with uniaxial strain along different crystallographic directions could, in principle, lead to the different compressions of the unit cell due to the anisotropy of the stiffness tensor of bulk SrTiO₃.⁶⁵ However, the resulting cleavage success and quality were comparable between the two differently oriented SrTiO₃, highlighting that the role of the pre-straining is primarily to confine the crack propagation during cleaving and indicating the generality of the approach.

The cleaved materials in Fig. 4 are cubic perovskites at room temperature, with the exception of BaTiO₃, which is cubic above 120 °C. SrTiO₃ and BaTiO₃ are nominally non-polar along the [001] direction (when neglecting the ferroelectric distortions of BaTiO₃). For KTaO₃, unreconstructed (001) surfaces are polar,^{66,67} and one of the mechanisms to compensate for the polarity is a high step density.⁶⁸ All materials exposed atomically flat surface areas with unit-cell high steps (≈ 0.4 nm) when cleaved this way. Cleaved KTaO₃(001) developed narrow terraces, while the atomically flat terraces are significantly larger on cleaved BaTiO₃(001). In both cases the step orientation is approximately parallel to the application of strain, along the [100] direction in this case. It is noteworthy that KTaO₃(001), unlike SrTiO₃, can also develop atomically flat surfaces after cleaving with a sharp tungsten carbide blade,⁶⁸ which could hold true for the truly ferroelectric BaTiO₃(001) as well. In either case, the application of the cleaving device still provides advantages with respect to its transferability and the creation of two research-ready surfaces.

SUMMARY

In summary, the procedure described in this work routinely produces bulk-terminated (001) surfaces of perovskites ABO₃ with large, atomically flat surface regions of both AO and BO₂ terminations. Well-cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface areas were found to always have the same chemical and physical properties, granting *a priori* knowledge of the surface structure. The distribution of the surface terminations on cleaved SrTiO₃ can be observed by SEM, while the conchoidally fractured and well-cleaved areas can be distinguished by an optical microscope alone. The creation of two mirror-symmetric, research-ready surfaces with each cleaving allows simultaneous measurements on two surfaces with opposite terminations. The method of cleaving by engineering the crack propagation via pre-straining single crystals was successfully applied to three cubic perovskite oxides, SrTiO₃, KTaO₃, and BaTiO₃, suggesting

general applicability. Together with the transferability of the cleaving device, this provides a convenient and reproducible pathway to obtaining truly bulk-terminated surfaces of this wide family of solids.

METHODS

For Fig. 1, the cleaving device was custom-made and home-built out of stainless steel, with more details laid out in the Appendix. The modeling, the calculations, and the results were performed and visualized using the Fusion 360 software by Autodesk®.

Single crystals used for cleaving were all procured in a custom shape and orientation:

- SrTiO₃(001) surfaces presented in Figs. 2 and 3 were obtained by cleaving single crystals with the orientation shown in Fig. 4(a). These SrTiO₃ crystals with a 3 × 7 mm² (110) face, a 2 × 7 mm² (1 $\bar{1}$ 0) face, and a 3 × 2 mm² (001) face were acquired from CrysTec GmbH, SurfaceNet GmbH, and MaTecK GmbH. Differently oriented and differently sized SrTiO₃(001) surfaces are shown only in Fig. 4(b): These custom shaped SrTiO₃ crystals with a 2 × 8 mm² (100) face, a 2 × 8 mm² (010) face, and a 2 × 2 mm² (001) face were acquired from MaTecK GmbH. All SrTiO₃ samples presented here had the same level of nominal Nb doping of 0.5 wt%. SrTiO₃ was routinely cleaved both in ambient and UHV. The majority of the samples were cleaved at room temperature.
- KTaO₃ samples cleaved in Fig. 4 were acquired from Stanford Advanced Materials in a custom shape with a 3 × 8 mm² (100) face, 1 × 8 mm² (010) face, and 1 × 2 mm² (001) face. The KTaO₃ samples were nominally undoped. The KTaO₃(001) surface in Fig. 4(c) was obtained by cleaving in ambient at room temperature.
- BaTiO₃ samples cleaved in Fig. 4 were acquired from MaTecK GmbH in a custom shape with a 3 × 8 mm² (100) face, a 3 × 8 mm² (010) face, and a 3 × 3 mm² (001) face. The BaTiO₃ samples were nominally undoped. The BaTiO₃(001) surface in Fig. 4(d) was obtained by cleaving in ambient at room temperature.

For Figs. 2(a)–2(c), the SEM images were acquired using the FEI Quanta 200F measurement setup, evacuated to a nominal vacuum of 1×10^{-5} mbar. An Everhart–Thornley detector was used for the detection of secondary electrons. All SEM images were acquired with an incident electron energy of 5 kV. SEM imaging was performed at the USTEM facility of the TU Wien. The two halves of the cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface shown in Figs. 2(a)–2(c) were exposed to ambient conditions during the transfer from a UHV laboratory to the USTEM facility. In fact, one of the surfaces was exposed to ambient conditions for over a month; however, the SEM contrast still showed clear contrast differences, consistent with the distribution of the two terminations on a cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface.

For Fig. 2(d), atomically resolved non-contact atomic force microscopy images of the two terminations on the cleaved SrTiO₃(001) surface were acquired in a low-temperature Omicron qPlus AFM/STM head. The measurement head is located in UHV with a base pressure below 10^{-11} mbar, and the measurements were performed at a temperature of 4.8 K. Cleavage was performed in a

connected UHV chamber with the base pressure below 10^{-10} mbar. The nc-AFM tips were prepared by electrochemically etching tungsten tips and subsequent cleaning *in situ* by self-sputtering with Ar^+ ions.³⁰ The tips were attached to custom-designed qPlus tuning forks with a separate wire for the tunneling current⁶⁹ at the end of the oscillating prong. The qPlus sensors had a resonance frequency of 28 kHz and a Q-factor of $\approx 50\,000$. The deflection signal of the oscillating prong was detected and measured using a cryogenic differential preamplifier.³² Low mechanical noise during measurement was achieved by decoupling the entire chamber from the surrounding vibrations by suspending it on bungee cords.³³

For Fig. 3, the optical photographs were acquired using the Olympus SZX12 microscope with an attached Olympus E-330 camera. All images were acquired with a similar orientation of the incident light. The orientation of the cleaved surfaces is indicated in the very first panel and is consistent on all other photographs. Each SrTiO_3 single crystal in Fig. 3 was 2 mm thick.

For Fig. 4, tapping-mode ambient AFM images were acquired using an Agilent 550 scanning probe microscope in an ambient atmosphere. The AFM cantilevers used were OLYMPUS OMCL-AC240TS with a reflective Al coating on the backside to reflect the incoming infrared laser used for detecting the deflection of the cantilever.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Igor Sokolović: Conceptualization (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (lead); Validation (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (lead). **Michael Schmid:** Formal analysis (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Ulrike Diebold:** Funding acquisition (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Martin Setvín:** Funding acquisition (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors will gladly provide further drawings of the cleaving device and any additional guidance upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX: PRACTICAL DETAILS OF THE PRE-STRAINING PROCEDURE

Bulk-truncated $\text{SrTiO}_3(001)$ surfaces can be systematically and reproducibly achieved with the pre-straining device depicted in Fig. 1(a). Good practices and common pitfalls regarding the construction, the pre-straining, and the cleaving procedure using this device are presented here using SrTiO_3 as an example.

Figure 1(a) shows detailed photographs of the cleaving device. The cleaving device consists of two identical clamping sets that squeeze a single crystal at the top and the bottom, such that they create a double-decker structure visible in photographs I and II in Fig. 1(a). Both the bottom and the top sets of clamps consist of a large and a small jaw; they are connected by two M2 screws. The small jaw has 2 mm diameter holes, while the large jaw has M2 threads at the corresponding positions. All jaws must be well polished in order to apply uniform pressure to the single crystal. The optimum polishing for the large jaws was found to be at a 5° angle at the face that will be touching the single crystal, such that the contact between the crystal and the jaws occurs in a very small area at the edge of the jaws, at the border of the volume where the cleavage should occur. This is depicted in the drawing V of Fig. 1(a). The quality of alignment is easily checked by placing the cleaving device, with a single crystal mounted inside, in front of a light source and verifying that the contact between the large jaw and a single crystal is as small as possible, as depicted in the photograph IV in Fig. 1(a). Each large jaw is fixed to its corresponding flag-type sample holder plates via an M2 screw. The small jaws, on the other hand, are free to move and are fixed to the large jaws by two M2 screws and applying pressure to the single crystal. For this reason, small jaws should not be polished with the same inclination as the large clamps, but perpendicular to the axes of the M2 clamping screws. When a crystal is clamped between the large and the small jaws, it will be lifted from the sample plate it previously stood on. This occurs due to the application of force to the single crystal, which inclines it toward the small jaw by an angle that cannot exceed the $\approx 5^\circ$ polishing angle of the large jaw.

The bottom and the top clamps are held together only via the squeezed single crystal between them. After a single crystal has been sufficiently squeezed by the bottom set of clamps, a small spacer needs to be inserted on top of the bottom part so that the top part can be mounted such that there is a small gap between the two parts of the double-decker construction. This gap [visible in the photographs marked III and IV in Fig. 1(a)] defines the crystal volume that is directly subjected to the uniaxial “squeezing” strain, and this is where the single crystal will eventually cleave. This separation can be easily achieved by placing two pieces of spacer sheet (0.1 mm thick) at each side of the clamped single crystal and resting the top set of clamps on top of them. After tightening the top set of clamps, they will no longer be parallel to the bottom set of clamps; instead, they will incline due to the inclination of the already squeezed single crystal along the large jaws.

The clamping procedure requires experience and caution. Proper alignment of the bottom set of clamps is crucial for ensuring a high-quality cleavage. Initially, the single crystal is placed on the sample plate close to the already fixed large bottom jaw, resting on the bottom face—in the case of SrTiO_3 , this was chosen to be the $(00\bar{1})$ face. The single crystal is then squeezed by tightening the M2 screws, which drive the small jaw toward the single crystal. It

is imperative that the gradual squeezing occurs in a way as equal as possible through the two M2 screws: if one side of the small bottom clamp is prematurely squeezing the crystal while the other side is still not in contact, the single crystal will be squeezed inhomogeneously. Once the small bottom jaw is securely in contact with the single crystal, as parallel as possible, the M2 screws need to be tightened with an appropriate torque. The exact value of torque necessary to ensure high-quality cleavage was not evaluated, but it is close to the force that would lead to damaging the screws. Applying too high a torque to the screws can crush the single crystal throughout the contact volume with the clamps, breaking it into fragments. The same can happen if the pre-straining is strongly asymmetric, in which case a single crystal is crushed on the side that is predominantly strained, which results in the damage of the entire single crystal. When the clamping with the bottom set of jaws is completed, tightening the top clamp is more challenging because this is the final step of preparation after which the sample is ready for cleaving. In other words, one has to take care not to induce a cleavage when mounting the top clamp. The complete cleaving device with the mounted sample is then transferred to UHV with caution to avoid accidental cleaving during transport, insertion into the load lock transfer arm, or insertion into a sample storage. The properly pre-squeezed crystals cleave with very little applied force.

Any material of choice for constructing the clamps can be used: so far we have tested clamps made out of stainless steel, molybdenum, and aluminum-zinc alloy (the latter not for use in UHV). Experience shows that stainless steel clamps are by far the best. A successful cleavage will leave an imprint on the steel clamps in the contact area with the sample due to the local plastic deformation following the application of strain during screw tightening. This imprint can also serve as an indicator of how strongly the sample was clamped, what the contact area with the sample was, and whether the clamping was properly parallel with respect to the face of the sample that was oriented toward the small jaw [normal to (001) in the case of SrTiO₃]. After each cleaving, all clamps have to be re-polished at those faces that were in contact with the sample in order to remove the plastically deformed material, visible as an imprint. This step usually requires very little polishing as the imprint into the stainless steel is not deep, i.e., gentle sandpaper is preferred for this step (we typically use grit 800, followed by 1200). After polishing, the entire device requires cleaning prior to the next mounting, and the stainless steel construction offers the possibility of boiling in 20% diluted HNO₃ for efficient cleaning. The only downside of the stainless steel cleaving device is that it cannot withstand high temperatures that would be used for investigating the effect of annealing on the cleaved surfaces, in which case molybdenum is the material of choice.

The sample is finally cleaved in UHV by pushing the ear of the flag-type sample holder plate that is a part of the top half of the double-decker shown in Fig. 1(a), using the UHV wobble stick. The bottom of the flag-type sample holder plates is preferably held inside the manipulator of the UHV chamber or the sample storage in UHV, whichever is sturdier. After cleaving, the bottom clamp with one half of the cleaved crystal remains in this position, while the top clamp with the remaining half of the cleaved crystal is held in the wobble stick by the ear of the flag-type sample holder plate. Therefore, a successful cleavage creates two well-defined SrTiO₃(001) surfaces, one held by the bottom clamp and the other held by the top clamp. Since

both are mounted on standardized flag-type sample holder plates, either or both can be used for subsequent measurements in UHV. Both the bottom and the top clamps are keeping the two halves of a cleaved single crystal firm enough that AFM/STM measurements can be performed at low temperatures, without interference from mechanical vibrations.

When a SrTiO₃ single crystal sample is properly pre-strained outside of UHV, very little force is necessary to cleave it with a wobble stick in UHV. The rule of thumb is that the easier the SrTiO₃ sample cleaves, the better the cleavage. In some cases, when the force required for cleaving was higher than simply touching the top part of the device, a successful cleavage could also be achieved, albeit with lower probability. When a single crystal requires a lot of force to cleave, it is better to stop the cleaving attempt and instead take the cleaving device outside of UHV for adjustments of the clamps and the application of higher strain to the single crystal. In the case of SrTiO₃, if a lot of force is required for cleaving, the sample will usually simply fracture conchoidally once sufficient force is applied.

The small size of the cleaving device limits the size of single crystals used for cleaving. The entire cleaving device is situated on an 18 × 15 mm² flag-type sample holder plate that is suited for a typical UHV system, namely for the wobble sticks, transfer arms, manipulators, sample storages, and the low-temperature AFM/STM head. A cleaving device with M2 screws [as the one in Fig. 1(a), technical drawings provided in Fig. 5] is close to the upper size limit for such UHV systems. A cleaving device with M3 screws is already not compatible with the size of the standard flag-type sample holder; in principle, it would be possible to have a cleaving device with M2.5 screws with reduced head sizes. The same considerations apply to

FIG. 5. Technical drawings of the (a) large jaw and the (b) small jaw. All units are given in millimeters.

the size of the SrTiO₃ single crystals designed for cleaving: their height is limited to ≈8 mm, but their width could be, in principle, as large as 5 mm and still fit into this cleaving device. However, cleaving 5 mm thick single crystals with this setup is challenging because only a limited amount of strain can be achieved using the M2 screws. If the cleaving device was not limited in size to fit on a standard flag-type sample holder plate, larger clamps and larger diameter screws could be used—these could apply higher forces and potentially enable successful cleaving of arbitrarily thick samples. Experience shows that the application of such larger clamps outside of UHV does enable easier cleaving.

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